

Electrical conductivity of Embroidery Design for Wearable Applications

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Abstract:

The smart textiles and allied wearable products increased their potential application in health care and device/system monitoring application. The emerging technology and traditional technology involved in such kind of new product development. The components involved in smart application devices are made with different kind of materials including flexible and hybrid materials from textiles. The traditional techniques, embroidery applied enormously for designing of smart components. Smart devices from embroidery technology satisfy the future requirements in terms of safety, control, fulfilment and entertainment. This first step of this investigation is aimed to optimize the parameters used for electrically conductive embroidery design by varying embroidery stitches, conductive yarn and total stitches in embroidery design. Computerized embroidery machine is used for the embroidery design development in a fabric. The electrical conductivity of the twenty five embroidery designs tested and analyzed using Design-expert-v12 software. The results revealed that the variables selected for the embroidery design having strong relationship with the electrical property of the fabric.

Keywords: *Conductive embroidery, conductive textiles, textile sensor, wearable electronics, computerized embroidery, filling stitches*

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1. Introduction

Smart textiles products realized through the developments in materials, processing and designing of a device components. The smart wearable system configuration facilitated by the industry and scientific community. For improving the functionality and usefulness, smart textile extends their application through passive smart textiles, active smart textiles and very smart textiles. The application of embroidery technology is higher in sensing and circuit integrations. The use of embroidery as single component or as a part of the device may reduce the cost involved in the whole system [1]. The polymeric materials can be made as sensors, actuators etc., called as electromechanical systems. The usage of textile components in smart system is increasing their potential applications. The conductive yarn usage and the level of stitch control with the specific combination pattern brings the possibilities of alternate source for the usage of electrical components such as capacitors, resistors etc., The conductive yarns used in embroidery process enables the integration with a device to study the electrical properties. The yarns used for embroidery process for the designing of conductive application, which allow the integration of yarns with various electrical properties.

The electrically conductive textiles includes interactive electronic textiles, location/position, infotainment, environmental response, biophysical monitoring (strategic/qualitative assessment only), government/public sectors, medical, commercial, industrial etc., the significant potential scope for the industrial sewing machines in wearable technology and e-textiles [2]. The cover stitch and over lock stitch is used to develop the sensor for the spinal bend measurement using 2-ply, 4-ply and 5-ply yarn. Wilcom ES, Ces_2000, Tajima DG/ML and Pre-design software used for the embroidery design punching for computerized embroidery machine. The angle of stitch, embroidery thread length in the design, stitch density and width of the filling are the properties of stitch category. Each running stitch used in embroidery machine has derivative stitches like simple stitch, straight

stitch and walk stitch. Based on the contour of the embroidery pattern the properties of the filling stitch varied. The filling stitches are satin, tatami and zigzag stitches which also have same properties [3]. The electrical conductivity of the closed circuit element developed with embroidery technique, the electrical conductivity of this system influenced by the form of design element, material property, direction of filling embroidery, process variables involved in embroidery process [4].

The embroidery technique preferred for the integration of flexible electronic modules. The metal and coated filaments are satisfying the integration conditions. Silver-coated polyamide yarn is used with linear stitch. The multiple sewing contacts were more beneficial for the reduction of yarn resistance compared to single stitch [5]. The simple line stitch, two line stitch and zig-zag stitch are developed for electrical path between press-studs. The silver yarn used with cotton yarn for developing electrical path to conductivity purpose. The zig-zag pattern consists of two line stitch used for the interconnection in smart T-shirt development [6]. The responsive key pad of the musical denim jacket adopted with embroidery technique. The conductive stainless steel wire and polyester composite thread used for developing the electrodes. The multiple interconnections of the single embroidery stitched electrodes increase the resistivity of the circuit and the use of tatami or satin stitches reduces the resistance per trace length [7]. Electrisola e-threads consist of seven filaments with 0.12 mm diameter used for the development of conductive dipole geometry textile antenna. The conductive threads used as a bobbin thread to achieve the conductive property and the needle thread acting as a couch for conductive thread [8]. The geometry shape embroidery antenna with higher accuracy developed by the author with fine details and proposed various shapes such as archimedian, toothed, sinusoidal and trapezoidal. Such kind of E-fiber antenna provides excellent performance with more flexibility [9]. The load current value for silver filament yarn and silver coated yarn used as heating element studied by the researchers and found that the fabric made with silver coated yarn load less than 0.1 A current, where as silver filament load over 0.3 A current [10].

In this direction, this fundamental preliminary work is focusing on the development of conductive embroidery design with various embroidery parameters. By analyzing the electrical property- Resistance (R) of the conductive embroidery design the optimized results were revealed.

2. Materials and Methods

The proposed/selected embroidery design and passage for the unbreakable needle thread were finalized based on various trials conducted during the conductive design production. The table1 and figure 1 shows the computerized embroidery machine particulars used for the development of conductive embroidery design.

2.1 Materials

The bleached woven fabric with plain weave used as ground fabric. The fabric made with the yarn linear density for the warp (Ne) =20, weft (Ne) =19.5, warp yarn density (epi) =46, weft yarn density (ppi) =45, linear weight of the fabric (gsm) =154 and cloth cover factor (K) =16.73 is used for the embroidery design development. The yarn particulars used in the embroidery process is tabulated in table 2.

Table 1- Computerized embroidery machine detail

Embroidery M/c	Computerized Embroidery machine
Make	M/s Barudan, Japan.
Model	BEVT-Z1501CBII
No. of Head	Single head
Embroidery Area	330X500/500
Number of needle used	1/15
M/c Speed (rpm)	20 rpm

Figure 1 - Computerized embroidery machine

Table 2 - Yarn used in Embroidery

Yarn type	Application	Yarn linear density
Copper coated yarn	Needle thread	3.8 Tex
Silver coated yarn		3.8 Tex
Zari coated yarn		3.8 Tex
Poly- yarn	Needle thread & bobbin thread	2/120 Denier

2.2 Methodology

The filling stitches in computerized embroidery machine satin, tatami and zigzag stitches used for the conductive fabric development with variation in number of stitches. The embroidery geometry design punching carried out using software (Wilcom ES). The figure 2 shows the two-step process for conductive embroidery fabric production. Three independent variables with its range and levels followed for the experimental study is tabulated in table 3. The zari, copper-coated and silver-coated yarns were sourced from woven fabric manufacturers around edappadi in Salem, Tamil Nadu, India. The current conductivity (mA) and electrical resistance (Ω) of the embroidery designed fabric studied to optimize the embroidery parameters.

The Design-expert-v12 software used to investigate the experiment efficiently with respect to mentioned variables to create respective response surface equation.

(a) Design punching

(b) Conductive embroidery design

Figure 2 - Conductive embroidery design production

Table 3 - Range of Variables

Parameters	Levels		
Number of Stitch (A)	1000	2000	3000
Conductive thread (B)	Zari coated (ZC)	Copper coated (CC)	Sliver coated (SC)
Stitch type (C)	Tatami	Satin	Zig-zag

2.3 Testing

The electrical properties such as current conductivity and electrical resistance of the embroidery fabrics analyzed based on the procedure given in section 2.3.1 and 2.3.2 respectively. The test result for the individual embroidery fabrics consolidated in table 4.

2.3.1 Current conductivity (I)

The rate at which the charge flows through the material is termed as electric current. The current conductivity of the embroidered fabrics is tested using Keithley Model 6517A Electrometer. 4Volt input is used to test all the embroidery samples. The average results for the each conductive designed fabric taken for the analysis.

2.3.2 Electrical Resistance (R)

Make current flow through a resistance there must be a voltage across that resistance. Ohm's Law shows the relationship between the three quantities such as voltage, current and resistance [11] is shown in equation (1).

$$\text{Resistance (R)} = V/I \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where,

V= Volt

I = Current (Amps)

Table 4 - Design of experiments- 2FI model and Response

Run	A-Stitches (Total numbers)	B-Conductive Thread (Type)	C-Stitch category (Type)	Resistance (Ω)	Current Conductivity (mA)
1	1000	ZC	Tatami	0.04	0.1
2	1000	ZC	Satin	0.01333	0.3
3	1000	ZC	Zigzag	0.02857	0.14
4	2000	ZC	Satin	0.00333	1.2
5	2000	ZC	Satin	0.00333	1.2
6	2000	ZC	Zigzag	0.02857	0.14
7	2000	ZC	Zigzag	0.02857	0.14
8	3000	ZC	Tatami	0.00333	1.2
9	1000	CC	Tatami	0.00049	8.1
10	1000	CC	Zigzag	0.00059	6.8
11	2000	CC	Tatami	0.00047	8.5
12	2000	CC	Satin	0.00043	9.3
13	2000	CC	Satin	0.00043	9.3
14	3000	CC	Tatami	0.00036	11
15	3000	CC	Satin	0.00031	12.7
16	3000	CC	Zigzag	0.00042	9.4
17	1000	SC	Tatami	0.00057	7
18	1000	SC	Satin	0.00053	7.5
19	1000	SC	Zigzag	0.00055	7.3
20	2000	SC	Tatami	0.00044	9
21	2000	SC	Satin	0.0004	10
22	2000	SC	Satin	0.0004	10
23	2000	SC	Zigzag	0.00051	7.8
24	2000	SC	Zigzag	0.00051	7.8
25	3000	SC	Tatami	0.00048	8.4

3. Results and Discussion

The results of the conductive embroidery fabric with respect to electrical property analyzed statistically. The model selected based on the highest order polynomials; in this the additional terms were significant.

The correlation coefficient R^2 value was important for validation of the model developed. The final empirical formula model for the response interms of coded factors is represented in equation [2]. The R^2 values for the response current conductivity (I) and the adjusted R^2 value are 0.9935 and 0.9859 respectively. The ANOVA values clearly indicate that the regression 2FI-model based on the equation it is significant ($F_{crit} > F_{actual}$) with actual F values. The model F value 130.09 for Current conductivity (I) is shown in table 5. The electrical property of the embroidery design imply the model is significant and the value of "F" is greater than 0.05 level.

$$\text{Current Conductivity (I)} = +6.11 + 1.27*A - 5.33*B[1] + 2.81*B[2] - 0.1169*C[1] + 0.8235*C[2] - 0.5932*AB[1] + 0.6764*AB[2] - 0.3720*AC[1] + 0.9946*AC[2] - 0.0108*B[1]C[1] + 0.3995*B[2]C[1] - 0.1434*B[1]C[2] - 0.2887*B[2]C[2] \dots\dots\dots (2)$$

Table 5 - ANOVA analysis for Current Conductivity (mA)

Source	Sum of squares	Degree of freedom (DF)	Mean square	F value	Prob>F
Model	407.03	13	31.31	130.09	< 0.0001
A-Stitches	14.91	1	14.91	61.96	< 0.0001
B-Conductive Thread	325.2	2	162.6	675.6	< 0.0001
C-Stitch category	6.94	2	3.47	14.41	0.0008
AB	3.09	2	1.54	6.41	0.0142
AC	3.58	2	1.79	7.43	0.0091
BC	1.74	4	0.4349	1.81	0.1978

3.1 Current Conductivity

The current conductivity of the embroidery fabric samples is evaluated and the 2FI model is achieved the 3D surface plots, the effect of conductive thread, stitch category on resistance (R) of surface embellished fabric at various stitch level has discussed. The significance and adequacy of the model justified through analysis of variance. The results are plotted in table 5 and figure 3, the model P-value (0.0001) less than 0.05 indicates terms are significant. The significant model terms are stitches (A), conductive thread (B) and stitch category (C). The embroidery design parameters A, B, C, AB and AC are significant model terms. The current conductivity of the embroidery design is more influenced by conductive yarn and stitch density (p-value = 0.0001) than stitch class (p-value = 0.0008). This may be the coated yarn conductivity property influences more significantly than stitch type. Irrespective of stitch level, the conductivity of the fabric produced with CC and SC produces higher conductivity (I) value than ZC conductive yarn.

At 1000 stitch among all conductive yarns, it is evident from the result the conductive design produced with ZC yarn have higher resistance (R) in conductivity. The satin stitched embroidery design provides higher current conductivity (I). This may be the closed stitches in density inside the contour design. The zigzag stitch produces wider in density of stitches than other filling stitches. Higher the density increases the number of contact point in yarn length, so current conductivity (I) also increased. The density characteristics of filling yarn influence the electrical conductivity of the design element [6]. The CC and SC yarns provide lower resistance value. This is because of resistivity of the material. The resistivity of copper and silver is $1.68 \times 10^{-8} \rho (\Omega \cdot m)$ and $1.59 \times 10^{-8} \rho (\Omega \cdot m)$ [11, 13].

In all stitch classes, when stitch density increases from 1000 to 3000 stitches, the closeness of the conductive yarn and the length of the yarn used for filling contour design also increased. So the resistance of the coated yarn increases linearly for CC, SC and ZC conductive embroidery fabrics. When increases in stitch density, electrical conductivity of the yarn and stitches type also influencing the electrical conductivity of the embroidery design. There is significant difference observed in between A and C, A and B parameters (p-value: 0.0091 and 0.0142 respectively which is <0.05 level). Satin stitch in an embroidery design contour produces closer and parallel stitches with each other. Whereas, tatami stitch provides closer stitches with the gap between stitch at the design

contour. Therefore, the length of the conductive thread consumed by the satin and tatami stitches also varied as 49.99 ft and 49.06 ft respectively for 1000 stitch density. The conductive fabric produced with satin stitch provides closer and more contact point between yarns. The author reported in their study, increases in stitch density and contour width, obtained stronger electrical conductivity [4].

The electrical property of the conductive samples produced with ZC yarn with zigzag stitch produces higher resistance (R) followed by tatami and satin stitched fabrics. The fabric produced with satin stitch combination produces lower resistance value. The satin stitch produces more parallel and closer stitches compared to other filling stitches. The number of stitch in a design, type of filling stitch and its geometry also influences the resistance of a conductive fabric.

Figure 3 - Electrical conductivity of embroidery design fabric

3.3 Optimization of Embroidery Parameters

The objective of the experimental design was to find the optimum embroidery parameters required for higher current conductivity through the embroidery design. The conductivity of the embroidery geometry design increased with increases in stitch density and vice versa. The target was set in design expert statistical software with higher electrical current conductivity. The optimum parameter was selected based on highest desirability. The figure 4 shows the optimum electrical conductivity value with suitable embroidery parameters as 3000 -stitch density, Satin -stitch type and Copper coated -conductive thread reveals highest desirability for the target.

Figure 4 - Optimized embroidery parameter

4. Conclusion

The embellished design in a fabric with conductive threads were developed using embroidery technique. The electrical conductivity of the developed fabric analyzed through the resistance and current conductivity of the embroidered article. The influence of embroidery stitch type, conductive threads at various stitch density studied and reveals the following conclusions.

- The current conductivity value of the embroidered design has significantly influenced by the selected embroidery parameters.
- At same design contour, increases in stitch density, electrical conductivity of sample influenced by the type of filling stitch and conductivity property of the embroidery yarn.
- Increases the stitch density from 1000 to 3000 stitches, the CC conductive thread with satin stitch combination provides higher current conductivity.

This kind of proposed surface embellished conductive fabric may suitable for low electrical conductivity application (4mA – 20mA) such as wearable sensors for measuring temperature, pressure, depth and humidity.

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